

BOOK of ABSTRACTS

International Conference
on Advanced Production and Processing

**2nd International Conference
on Advanced Production and Processing
20th-22nd October 2022
Novi Sad, Serbia**

Title:

Book of Abstracts of the 2nd International Conference on Advanced Production and Processing publishes abstracts from the following fields: Innovative Food Science and Bioprocesses, Nutraceuticals and Pharmaceuticals, Sustainable Development, Chemical and Environmental Engineering, Materials Design and Applications, Petroleum Refining and Production.

Publisher:

University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technology Novi Sad,
Bulevar cara Lazara 1, 21000 Novi Sad, Serbia

For publisher:

prof. Biljana Pajin, PhD, Dean

Editorial board:

Jovana Petrović, Ivana Nikolić, Milica Hadnađev Kostić, Snežana Škaljac, Milana Pribić, Bojan Miljević, Branimir Pavlić, Olga Govedarica

Editor-in-Chief:

Prof. Zita Šereš, PhD

Design and Printing Layout:

Saša Vulić

CIP - Каталогizacija u publikaciji
Biblioteke Matice srpske, Novi Sad

658.5(048.3)

INTERNATIONAL Conference on Advanced Production and Processing (2 ; 2022 ; Novi Sad)
Book of abstracts [Elektronski izvor] / 2nd International Conference on Advanced Production and Processing, 20th-22nd October 2022, Novi Sad ; [editor-in-chief Zita Šereš]. - Novi Sad : Faculty of Technology, 2022

Način pristupa (URL): <https://www.tf.uns.ac.rs/download/icap-2022/book-of-abstracts.pdf>. - Opis zasnovan na stanju na dan 14. 10. 2022. - Nasl. s naslovnog ekrana.

ISBN 978-86-6253-160-5

a) Tehnologija - Proizvodnja - Apstrakti

COBISS.SR-ID 77341961

**2nd International Conference
on Advanced Production and Processing
20th-22nd October 2022
Novi Sad, Serbia**

CONFERENCE CHAIRMAN

Prof. Biljana Pajin, Dean of the Faculty of Technology Novi Sad

HONORARY COMMITTEE

Professor Marijana Carić,

Emeritus Professor at University of Novi Sad, Serbia

Professor Radmila Marinković Nedućin,

Emeritus Professor at University of Novi Sad, Serbia

Professor Miodrag Tekić,

Emeritus Professor at University of Novi Sad, Serbia

Professor Vladimir Srdić,

Corresponding member of Serbian Academy of Sciences and Arts,

Faculty of Technology Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

Professor Jasna Čanadanović–Brunet,

highest cited professor at Faculty of Technology

Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

ORGANISING COMMITTEE

from the Faculty of Technology Novi Sad, University Novi Sad, Serbia

Prof. Zita Šereš

Prof. Jaroslav Katona

Prof. Nataša Đurišić Mladenović

Prof. Lidija Petrović

Prof. Jelena Pejin

Prof. Dragan Govedarica

Prof. Senka Vidović

Prof. Jelena Pavličević

Prof. Bojana Ikonić

Prof. Ljiljana Popović

Prof. Marija Milanović

Prof. Ivana Nikolić

Prof. Milica Hadnađev Kostić

Prof. Olga Govedarica

Prof. Jadranka Fraj

Prof. Senka Popović

Prof. Marija Jokanović

Prof. Zorica Stojanović

Branimir Pavlić, Assistant Professor

Uroš Miljić, Assistant Professor

Snežana Škaljac, Senior Research Associate

Sanja Panić, Senior Research Associate

Bojan Miljević, Senior Research Associate

Jovana Petrović, Research Associate

Mirjana Petronijević, Research Associate

Vesna Vasić, Research Associate

Ana Đurović, Research Associate

Aleksandra Cvetanović Kljakić, Research Associate

Nataša Nastić, Research Associate

Ljiljana Spasojević, Research Assistant

Jelena Tanasić, Research Assistant

Andrea Nesterović, Research Assistant

Milana Pribić, Teaching Assistant

Julijana Blagojević, Teaching Assistant

Jelena Škrbić, Research Trainee

Sonja Stojanov, Research Trainee

SCIENTIFIC COMMITTEE

- Prof. Viktor Nedović, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Belgrade, Serbia
- Prof. Zorica Knežević-Jugović, Faculty of Technology and Metallurgy, University of Belgrade, Serbia
- Anamarija Mandić, Principal Research Fellow, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
- Prof. Verica Dragović-Uzelac, Faculty of Food Technology and Biotechnology, University of Zagreb, Croatia
- Prof. Dragana Šoronja Simović, Faculty of Technology Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
- Prof. Sandra Budžaki, Faculty of Food Technology, Josip Juraj Strossmayer University of Osijek, Croatia
- Prof. Sonja Smole Možina, Biotechnical Faculty, University of Ljubljana, Slovenia
- Prof. Drago Šubarić, Faculty of Food Technology, Josip Juraj Strossmayer University of Osijek, Croatia
- Prof. Zsuzsanna László, Faculty of Engineering, University of Szeged, Hungary
- Prof. Aleksandra Tepić Horecki, Faculty of Technology Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
- Vesna Đorđević, Principal Research Fellow, Institute of Hygiene and Meat Technology, Belgrade, Serbia
- Prof. Małgorzata Korzenowska, Wrocław University of Environmental and Life Sciences, Poland
- Prof. Cecilia Hodúr, Faculty of Engineering, University of Szeged, Hungary
- Prof. Gordana Dimitrovska, Faculty of Biotechnical Sciences, University "St. Kliment Ohridski", Bitola, Macedonia
- Prof. Borislav Malinović, Faculty of Technology, University of Banja Luka, Bosnia and Herzegovina
- Prof. Zoran Zeković, Faculty of Technology Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
- Prof. Ljijana Đekić, Faculty of Pharmacy, University of Belgrade, Serbia
- Prof. Predrag Putnik, Department of Food Technology, University of the North, Croatia
- Prof. Rita Ambrus, Inst. of Pharmaceutical Technology and Regulatory Affairs Faculty of Pharmacy, University of Szeged, Hungary
- Prof. Vlada Veljković, Corresponding Member of Serbian Academy of Sciences and Arts, Faculty of Technology in Leskovac, University of Niš, Serbia
- Perica Bošković, Assistant Professor, Faculty of Chemistry and Technology, University of Split, Croatia
- Prof. Olivera Stamenković, Faculty of Technology in Leskovac, University of Niš, Serbia
- Prof. Gülsün Akdemir Evrendilek, Bolu Abant İzzet Baysal University, Bolu, Turkey
- Marinella Farré, Principal Research Fellow, Institute of Environmental Assessment and Water Research, CSIC, Barcelona, Spain
- Prof. João Crespo, NOVA School of Science and Technology, Universidade Nova de Lisboa, Portugal
- Prof. Zoran Petrović, Full member of Serbian Academy of Sciences and Arts, Kansas Polymer Research Center, Pittsburg State University, Pittsburg, USA
- Prof. Vladimir Srdić, Corresponding member of Serbian Academy of Sciences and Arts, Faculty of Technology Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
- Prof. Branka Pilić, Faculty of Technology Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
- Branko Matović, Principal Research Fellow, Vinča Institute of Nuclear Sciences, University of Belgrade, Serbia,
- Prof. Ana Brás, Faculty of Engineering and Technology, Liverpool John Moores University, United Kingdom
- Lucretia Miu, Principal Research Fellow, National Research & Development Institute for Textile and Leather, Bucharest, Romania
- Polonca Ropret, Principal Research Fellow, Head of Research Institute at Institute for the Protection of Cultural Heritage of Slovenia, University of Ljubljana, Slovenia
- Prof. Alexander Knyazev, Chemical Faculty, Lobachevsky State University of Nizhni Novgorod, Russia
- Prof. Dmitry Grishin, Full member of Russian Academy of Sciences, Lobachevsky State University of Nizhni Novgorod, Russia
- Prof. Blaž Likozar, National Institute of Chemistry, Slovenia

EFFECT OF HIGH AND LOW HUMIDITY ON THE RELEASE OF LAMOTRIGINE FROM IMMEDIATE RELEASE TABLET FORMULATIONS

Gordana Švonja Parezanović¹, Mladena Lalić-Popović¹, Nemanja Todorović¹, Jelena Čanji Panić¹, Nataša Milošević¹

¹ *University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Medicine, Department of Pharmacy, Hajduk Veljkova 3, Novi Sad 21000, Serbia*

Storage of drugs in different climatic conditions, often without primary packaging, separately in dispensers for weekly or monthly therapy, causes exposure to increased or decreased humidity relative to standard humidity, which threatens the stability of the drug and its safety. The aim of this study was to examine whether there is a difference between the original formulation of lamotrigine tablets with immediate release (original formulation) and selected generic formulations ($n = 3$) in terms of tablet characteristics (disintegration, hardness, moisture content and weight variation) and lamotrigine release profile when exposed to increased ($75\% \pm 5\%$) and decreased humidity ($30\% \pm 5\%$) at room temperature ($25^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$). Four formulations of immediate release lamotrigine tablets were used. The Fa formulation is original, while the Fb, Fc and Fd formulations are generic formulations. Physical characteristics of LTG tablets were determined according to the European Pharmacopoeia. The dissolution profile comparison was carried out using model-independent (statistical) and model-dependent (kinetic) methods to provide detailed information about dissolution data. Dissolution tests were conducted using a validated UV/VIS spectrophotometric method. Dissolution characteristics of the tablet formulations were evaluated at three points spanning the physiological pH range (pH 1.2, pH 6.8). The Fc formulation showed the largest difference in composition, disintegration and wetting time, as well as in the drug release profile. All formulations had a reduction in hardness in high humidity conditions (75%). Exposure of the formulations to conditions of high and low humidity caused a change in the release profile of LMT and led to the said formulations not releasing more than 85% of the contents in the first 15 minutes, which is allowed by the pharmacopoeia. The effect of high humidity conditions is more pronounced on reduced LMT release compared to low humidity conditions. In pH 6.8 medium, the dissolution profile of the Fc formulation shows a statistically lower release / dissolution of LMT at all time points compared to the Fa, Fb and Fd formulations. The cause of the slower release of LMT from the Fc formulation compared to other tested formulations is probably the presence of calcium carbonate in the formulation. These results clearly indicate that storage of tablet formulations in conditions of high and low humidity not only affect the tablet characteristics of the formulation, but also the dissolution rate of LMT.

Keywords: Lamotrigine tablets, Humidity, Tablet characteristics, Dissolution

Acknowledgements: Project of Ministry Education, Science and Technology of Republic of Serbia [451-03-68/2022-14/200114].